

FEEDBACK OF PRE SERVICE TEACHERS REGARDING THE COURSE

‘UNDERSTANDING SELF’

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Abstract

The present study focuses on analysis of the feedback given by Pre Service Teachers related to the course ‘Understanding Self’ in Bachelor of Education Two Years program. The objective of the study was to collect feedback and analyze responses focusing Life Skills. Survey method followed for collecting the feedback. Feedback sheet was a research tool having both closed and open ended questions. Only closed ended questions were analyzed in the study. Findings show that the responses of the pre service teacher indicate the life skills and how Life Skills can be included in the pre service teachers curriculum through the activities planned systematically in the course Understanding Self.

Key words: *Pre Service Teacher, Feedback, Life Skills*

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Introduction: The NEP 2020 emphasizes on moving from rote learning to enabling the learners to develop Life Skills so as to lead a competent, successful and an effective life. Life skills play an important role in how effectively a person deals with the various complexities that occur in their lives. Naturally life skills education should be an integral part of the Teacher education program. Good trained teachers who understand their own self in the context of Life Skills would be better equipped to impact it to their students in the classroom.

Need and Importance of the Study: Life skills are crucial for pre-service teachers as they support personal all round development and enhance their performance in the school classroom. The life skill Self-awareness helps pre-service teacher to enable them in understanding own strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, and also biases. They learn to manage their thoughts, feelings, and behaviours effectively, promoting self-regulation and emotional intelligence. This self-awareness allows them to deal with challenging situations, handle stress, and maintain a positive mind set, which are essential for their overall development and classroom management.

The life skills placed under the category of Social skills like Communication skills are essential for Pre-service teachers because strong communication and interpersonal

relationship helps them to establish positive relationships with their students, parents, colleagues, and other stakeholders. These skills enable teachers to connect with their students, understand their needs, and address any issues that may arise.

Critical thinking, Creative thinking and problem-solving skills are placed under the category of Thinking skills.. With these skills Pre service teacher learns to analyze situations, assess and evaluate information, and make informed decisions. These skills helps teachers to design activity based innovative and engaging lesson plans, cater to the diverse learning needs, and address challenges in the classroom effectively.

In summary, life skills are essential for pre-service teachers as they support personal development, well-being, and professional effectiveness. These skills enhance their self-awareness, communication abilities, critical thinking, enabling them to create positive and impactful learning experiences for their students.

Review of the Related Literature: WHO Guidelines published in 1997 regarding facilitating and development and Implementation of Life Skills Programme contains methods of teaching life skills. This document mentions methods to teach life skills viz. active involvement include working in small groups and pairs, brainstorming, role play, games and debates. Guidelines also informs about training on the basis of participatory learning in groups. The study undertaken by Baloyi L T (1998) titled An evaluation of the "Life Skills Train the Trainer Programme" University of South Africa opined that In life skills education, Children and adolescents are actively involved in a dynamic teaching and learning process that is often based on Bandura's Social Learning Theory which declares that self instruction is the most effective learning techniques for skill development. Experiential learning, co operative learning, Group Work are useful methods of teaching. The instructor should become a manager and non judgemental facilitator for self discovery and self directed learning for the learners. Wurdinger S, Qureshi M (2014) examined whether life skills could be developed in a Project Based Learning (PBL) course. Findings of the study reveal that Project based learning allowed students to practice and develop life skills. Borg (2011) examined the impact of in service teacher education programme in United Kingdom on the beliefs of Six English language teachers. The study suggested that programme has a impact on the teachers beliefs. The study done by Yildirim, G. (2019) examined what pre-service teachers understood from the concept of "basic life skills", how they dealt with the concept and what they associated the concept with.

Significance of the Review in Present Study: WHO Guidelines helped the researcher in deciding activities to be planned in the course. The research done by Baloyi L T helped researcher in deciding methods of teaching for the course.

Statement of the Problem: To analyze the feedback of Pre service teachers regarding the course Understanding Self.

Objectives of the study:

1. To collect feedback of the students teachers regarding the course Understanding Self
2. To analyze students responses focusing Life Skills

Research Question: Whether student teachers feedback about the course Understand self, reflect life skills?

Assumptions: The life skills like Problem solving, decision making, critical thinking are directly related with the subject studies. The students should get an opportunity to learn subject studies through these skills. (SCF 2010)

Scope, Limitations and Delimitations of the study:

- **Scope:** Present study focuses on the course Understanding Self as an effective teaching strategy for Second Year Bachelor of Education students to develop life skills
- **Delimitations:** The study is delimited to one Teacher Education Institute in Pune city having English and Marathi as medium of Instruction, receiving Grant in aid from Govt of Maharashtra and runs as a co education institute affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University (SPPU)
- **Limitations:** Fatigue, Past Experiences, mood and and motivation levels of Student Teachers which may affect their responses are beyond the control of the researcher.

Research Methodology: For collecting feedback researcher used Survey Method. In Covid 19 lockdown conditions, post 16th March 2020 Student teachers of Second Year are located at their homes and in geographically distant places form the college. So to seek opinion of the students, researcher decided to use survey method

Population and Sample:

All students of Second Year Bachelor of Education course enrolled in recognized teacher education institutes affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University in Pune city was the population for present study.

92 students of the Bachelor of Education course enrolled in Adarsha Comprehensive College of Education and Research affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University was the sample.

Research Tools: A feedback sheet has been used for data collection. Feedback sheet is a Rating Scale consisted of Statement related to Orientation and activity Sessions. Feedback sheet also contains open ended questions.

Course Background:

Adarsha Comprehensive College of Education and Research follows the syllabus prescribed by Savitribai Phule Pune University. Present Bachelor of Education syllabus is a Choice Based Credit System Two year course effective from the Academic Year 2015-16.

Two credits allocated for Course 209 Understanding Self for Second Year B.Ed. The learning load is of 32 clock hours. Syllabus contains course objectives and it informs the stakeholders the manner in which the course should be conducted. The course consists of four Orientation and four Activity Sessions.

Course Delivery:

Researcher framed learning outcomes before beginning of academic year. Decided the themes for orientation sessions and activity sessions. Activities were designed by keeping view of the selected life skills like Critical thinking, Creative thinking, Problem solving, Communication Skills, Empathy etc. Following activities were planned for the delivery of Course BED 209 - Group Discussion, Speeches, Drawing / Painting and Facing Interview.

Rationale behind selecting Group Discussion activity- Students learn to work in group, listens to others views, sometime they learn to accept views of the others. Group discussion activity helps to improve presentation skills, negotiation skills, communication skills

Rationale behind selecting Speech activity – Researcher searched and identified speeches delivered by iconic personalities in the areas of Education and Environment. These speeches were available on You Tube in public domain. As these speeches focus on Educational and Environmental issues students will think critically, will try to find out solutions.

Rationale behind selecting Drawing Painting activity – With this activity students will use their Creative abilities, use original ideas.

Rationale behind selecting Facing the Interview activity – Researchers has decided introduction of Role Play method for this activity. So participating in this activity, student will assume a specific role. They will collaborate in their own Micro group. So communication skills, Interpersonal relationship skill will develop.

Data Analysis:

Table 1 Responses for Orientation Sessions

Sr. No.	Statement	Response			
		S. A.	Agree	Disagree	S.D.
After Orientation Sessions now I can					
1	list the life skills included in the school syllabus	56.4	36.4	0	7.2
2	narrate the meaning of empathy and its importance in democracy.	54.5	41.9	0	3.6
3	explain how life skills are interrelated with each other.	52.7	40.0	0	7.3
4	Explain the meaning of Creative Thinking and its relevance in understanding the self	40.2	52.6	1.8	5.5
5	Use synectics model of teaching in school classroom	29.1	58.1	7.3	5.5
6	explain how creative thinking is useful skill in problem solving.	45.4	47.3	1.8	5.5
7	Explain the dimensions of self concept and state the importance of developing self concept	38.3	56.3	1.8	3.6
8	Describe the difference between Self concept and Self Esteem	32.7	58.2	5.5	3.6
9	Explain the difference between Bio Data, Resume and Curriculum Vitae	49.1	45.5	1.8	3.6
10	Describe important elements of Bio data, resume and Curriculum vitae	41.9	50.9	3.6	3.6
11	Try to do SWOT analysis of self	34.5	58.2	5.5	1.8
12	Draft own Resume / Bio data	42.5	55.6	1.9	0

Observations: From the above table we can observe that the majority of the students have given their responses in the Strongly Agree or Column A. The responses indicate that they are able to enlist, explain, describe the different Life Skills. Further they are able to do activities which reflect their understanding of Life Skills.

Interpretation: Responses of the Pre service teachers reflect the life skills Empathy, Creative Thinking, Self Awareness.

Table 2 Responses for Activity Session – Group Discussion

Sr. No.	Statement	Response			
		S. A.	Agree	Disagree	S.D.
During Group Discussion I					
1	Participated actively in the group discussion session.	67.3	27.3	3.6	1.8
2	And my team found out solution for a particular issue through dialogue	49.1	45.5	1.8	3.6
3	examined an allotted theme from various perspectives during the group discussion session.	47.3	49.1	1.8	1.8
4	Recorded thoughts and accepted which were appropriate presented by other students	38.2	58.2	1.8	1.8
5	Communicated successfully with other students	60.0	38.2	0	1.8
6	Now I can form and express my own opinion on policy matters.	38.2	58.2	1.8	1.8

Observations: The activity Group Discussion has helped the pre service teachers in actively participating in the Group Discussion, also solve problems using Critical Thinking, having effective dialogue with others and learning to accept the rationally presented thoughts by other participants.

Interpretation: Responses of the Pre service teacher indicate that the activity Group discussion is useful to develop life skills Problem Solving, Critical Thinking, Effective Communication, and Empathy

Table 3 Responses for Activity Session – Speeches

Sr. No.	Statement	Response			
		S. A.	Agree	Disagree	S.D.
1	Worked in pairs / small group to prepare reflection on speech	40.0	54.5	1.8	3.6
2	Expressed my views effectively	45.5	50.9	1.8	1.8
3	Got motivation from the speech to do something for society	49.1	47.3	0	3.6
4	Delivered the reflections on speech confidently	52.7	45.5	0	1.8

Observations: The speeches activity has helped the students to interact in pairs or groups and express their views / reflections. Also it has been made them aware of various social issues.

Interpretation: Responses of the pre service teacher indicate that the activity Speeches indicate the life skills Effective Communication, Interpersonal Relationship, Empathy

Table 4 Responses for Activity Session – Drawing Painting and Craft

Sr. No.	Statement	Response			
		S. A.	Agree	Disagree	S.D.
Before During and After the activity Drawing Painting and Craft --					
1	Searched and gathered information related to selected theme using online and offline resources	54.5	41.8	1.8	1.8
2	Wrote a supportive text the theme for a drawing / picture	45.5	50.9	1.8	1.8
3	effectively presented my creation in online session	41.8	50.9	5.5	1.8
4	After the activity Drawing / Painting I gained Self-confidence about own creativity	52.7	45.5	1.8	0.0

Observations: The responses highlight that the activity helped to make the students active participants and also self-learners. It also helped to increase their confidence and realize their own Creative Self.

Interpretation: The responses highlight the learning of life skills like Critical Thinking, Creative Thinking, and Communications Skills through this activity.

In the activity – Drawing Painting and Craft students have been asked to record their responses regarding theme of the drawing. Analysis of the responses depicted in the following table.

Table 5 Themes Selected by Participants for Drawing / Painting

Theme of the Drawing	% of respondents
Online Classroom	10.9
Fiction and Fantasy in Science	9.1
Dream city 2023- My Vision	3.6
Where do you see yourself after Five Years	18.2
Hope and Positivity	16.4
Child Rights	17.0
Environment in 2030	9.1
Coping with Stress	18.2

Observations: The selected themes show a variety. The most like theme is ‘Where do you see yourself after five years’, followed by Child Rights and then by Hope and Positivity. All these themes reflect the Life Skills namely Empathy, Communication Skills Critical Thinking, Problem Solving.

Interpretation: The drawing painting activity conducted in the course reflects all the Life Skills which the researcher had included in the sessions.

Table 6 Responses for Activity Session – Facing Interview

Sr. No.	Statement	Response			
		S. A.	Agree	Disagree	S.D.
After the activity Facing Interview I felt that I can					
1	Collaborated with my Micro group colleagues	65.5	30.9	1.8	1.8
2	listen carefully questions asked by Interviewer/ answers given by Interviewee	44.4	53.7	1.9	0
3	Participate in a simulated/ regular employment interview	33.3	64.8	1.9	0
4	Enlist the errors made by self / others in a interview	31.5	63	5.6	0
5	Express my thoughts confidently to the interviewer / or as a Interview panel member	50	0	16.7	33.3

Observations: Majority of the responses are in the Strongly Agree (SA) or Agree (A). The Interview activity focused on use of the Life Skills which the researcher had planned to imbibe through the program. A good percentage of students was able to analyse themselves thus the Understanding Self.

Interpretation: The facing Interview activity helped the pre service teachers to make actual use of the Life Skills which the resource person had tried to inculcate through the theory sessions.

Conclusion: The study show how Life Skills can be included in the pre service teachers through the activities planned systematically in the course Understanding Self. They would make them better equipped personally, socially and professionally.

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